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A STUDY ON THE USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract:

This study aimed to see how social media is used by undergraduate students and how it affects their academics as well as their social life in colleges. Participants consisted of undergraduate students aged 18 and older (N=116). In order to obtain data on this topic, students were asked to participate via online survey. Students expressed what types of social media they use, such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and SnapChat. They were also asked how much time they spend on social media, their current GPA (grade point average) and whether their GPA has increased or decreased due to the amount of time they spend using social media. Data was analyzed using SPSS.

Introduction

Social media, such as Facebook, Twitter, etc., has taken the technology world to a whole new level. Although we see how it can serve as a positive thing by being a good source of communication, it can also serve as a negative thing such as cyber bullying and the new phrase "cat fishing." But what happens when social media use comes in to play with academics on an undergraduate level? The purpose of my study is to see how social media use by undergraduate students affects their

academics as well as their social life in college. My hypothesis would be that social media use by undergraduate students would positively affect their academics and social life in college. I believe that my hypothesis will be supported because; social media can be used for different aspects of academics. Nowadays, professors encourage their students to use social media to either be kept up to date with things that are going on in the classroom or even using it for educational research. Also, some professors use social media for classroom assignments, which enable the

students to keep in contact with one another in regards to class work.

Michikyan, Subrahmanyam, & Dennis, (2015) conducted research on Facebook use and how it affects college students and their academic performance. They have found that students with lower GPAs are involved with more activity on Facebook than students with higher GPAs. Research by Michikyan (2015a) stated that "However, our findings imply that students who are experiencing difficulties at college and who are not fully engaged in their studies may be those who are most likely to turn to Facebook for distraction and entertainment or even to cope with their frustrations." Using social media to cope with academic frustrations can be a good outlet, especially if the student is connecting with another student that is having the same problem. Social media allows students to get connected with other students, which can be very beneficial because it can allow them to discuss class material via social media as well as help them by network.

The key parts measured in this study are the type of social media used, how often it is used, when it is typically used, and the effect it has on academics such as GPA. The significance of the

study was to be able to show undergraduate students that social media can positively affect their academics as well as increase their networking skills with other classmates.

One limitation is that everyone may not participate in the survey given to measure how much time the students spend on social media. The students may also not be truthful when answering the questions, which could alter results. Assumptions that can be made is that the study will be geared towards regular education students, which would exclude all special education students such as students who receive special accommodations for their academics. It will also be taken into consideration that the number of men and women who will be taking the survey will not be equal and their class level will not all be the same, for example, not everyone taking the survey will be seniors, juniors, etc. Instead, their class level will vary across the board. Conducting research on this topic can be beneficial for many undergraduate students as well as graduate students. The information gathered throughout this study will also be beneficial to me as well. It will be neat to see how the use of social media can increase GPAs.

Method

The method adopted for this study was survey. The survey aimed to ask the participants about their social media use, academics, and their GPA (grade point average). The introduction to the survey lasted approximately three minutes, the survey took no longer than 10 minutes to complete, and the debriefing lasted approximately three minutes. An intervention was not needed for this study.

Design

The study conducted used a correlational design. The independent variable was social media use and the dependent variable was GPA and whether it increased or decreased.

Sampling

Convenience sample size consisted of 116 participants. Participants consisted of undergraduate students who remain completely anonymous. Inclusion criteria were male and female undergraduate students. The starting age for participants was 18, but there is no end age because not everyone who is in undergraduate courses is the same age. Ethnicity and socioeconomic status were not considered issues in regards to the study. Exclusion criteria consisted of graduate students and students with special needs.

Participants were notified about the study and its survey via e-mail, and/or their professor. The survey was free to take part in, but as far as compensation, their professor may offer extra credit for partaking in the survey.

Results

The study aimed to examine the relationship between GPA and how much time undergraduate students spend using social media. SPSS was used to analyze and interpret the data received from the survey. After the data was analyzed, it was shown there was no correlation between GPA and the amount of time spent using social media. Although our results do not agree with the hypothesis, results show that it was not significant ($r = -.236$, $p = .011$). The study showed that a student's GPA is more likely to decrease due to the amount of time spent using social media.

0.8- 4.2% of students had a GPA between 2.00-2.50. 0.8-9.2% of students had a GPA between 2.51-3.00. 0.8-9.2% of students had a GPA between 3.01-3.50. 0.8-9.2% of students had a GPA between 3.51-4.00. In regards to change in GPA, 25% of students declined to answer, while 38% of students claimed that their GPA increased and 38% of students claimed that their GPA decreased. Current GPA

($M=3.2465$, $SD=.4600$), Change in GPA ($M=1.11$, $SD=.789$).

Conclusion

It was hypothesized that social media use by undergraduate students would positively affect their academics and social life in college. The results found do not agree with the original hypothesis, meaning that social media use by undergraduate students does not positively affect their academics and social life in college. Previous research supports the findings and assumption that there is an approaching significance between social media use and GPA.

In conclusion, undergraduate students should monitor how much time they spend using different types of social media. Social media can be beneficial when it comes to academics, such as discussion boards amongst classmates, Facebook pages for school programs, etc. Social media can also be beneficial for social adjustment amongst undergraduate students. Research by Yang and Brown (2015) found that "Facebook is useful in maintaining social connections, leading them to spend more time using the site, which contributed to better social adjustment in college. They engaged in more Facebook interaction with on-campus friends, which in turn

facilitated social adjustment in college and satisfaction with college life." Although undergraduate students are always using social media, it is important that they maintain a healthy balance between how much time they spend using social media, and how much time they spend on their academics.

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